

Effect of Gamma Radiation on the Chemical Durability of Glass Fibrous Insulation Used in Nuclear Power Plants

J. Vráblová¹, M. Liška¹, M. Chromčíková¹, J. Michálková¹, H. Kaňková¹, V. Soltész²

¹FunGlass – Vitrum Laugaricio – Joint Glass Center of IIC SAS, TnU AD, and FChPT STU

Študentská 2, Trenčín, SK – 911 50, Slovak Republic

(E-mail: jana.vokelova@tnuni.sk, marek.liska@tnuni.sk, maria.chromcikova@tnuni.sk,
jaroslava.michalkova@tnuni.sk, hana.kankova@tnuni.sk)

²VUEZ, Hviezdoslavova 35, P.O. Box 153, Levice, SK-943 39, Slovakia

(E-mail: soltesz@vuez.sk)

ABSTRACT

In case of an accident the emergency system of a nuclear power plant is used in order to preserve pressure of a coolant in the primary cooling circuit and to dispose from the active zone of nuclear reactor. The system consists of the tanks filled with the boric acid solution and the pumps transporting solution to the primary cooling area. Moreover the low-pressure pumps are activated when the tanks are not able to bring the cooling solution into the system. After pumping out, the cooling solution is pumped in again from the heat exchanger placed at the bottom of the hermetic boxes. Loss of coolant accident – LOCA (damage of the primary cooling area) causes rapid increase of pressure in the hermetic boxes. Therefore the spraying system is activated. Required decrease of pressure is achieved by spraying the area of the hermetic boxes and by condensation of steam and air mixture. The glass fibers play a significant role regarding the security system of the nuclear plants. Glass fibers are mainly used as thermal and electrical insulation and in case of accident fibers get in immediate contact with cooling solution. It is well known that water solution in contact with a glass causes changes resulting in the structure transformation of glass surface, dissolution of a glass itself and formation of new glass surface layer.

The chemical durability of gamma-irradiated glass fibrous insulation commonly used in the reactor containment of nuclear power plants was tested by static leaching tests at 70, 80 and 90°C. Distilled water was used as corrosive medium. Two radiation doses, 2 and 4 MGy, were applied, the higher one roughly corresponding to 30 years of irradiation in reactor containment. The glass insulation was irradiated at low (70°C) and increased (450°C) temperatures. The results of the static leaching tests were compared with those obtained for non-irradiated native glass fibers. Therefore, the aim of the present work is the study of influence of gamma irradiation and temperature on the chemical durability of glass fibers. This will be quantified by static leaching tests of non-irradiated native glass fibers and irradiated glass fibers performed in distilled water. The detailed analysis of results of static and flow thorough leaching tests leads to the hypothesis of quasi congruent glass dissolution. Using this assumption the leaching kinetics was described by the Aagaard Helgeson equation. The kinetic parameters were obtained by the non-linear regression analysis of time evolution of leaching solution composition.

Keywords: Glass fibers, corrosion, LOCA, chemical durability, gamma radiation, static leaching tests.

Acknowledgment:

This paper is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.

This work was supported by The Slovak Grant Agency for Science under grant No. VEGA 2/0088/16, VEGA 1/0064/18 and APVV 0487-11.

References:

/1/ MIŠÍKOVÁ, L. - GALUSKOVÁ, D.: *Corrosion of e-glass fibers – security factor of nuclear power plants*, *Ceramics – Silikáty*, 50 (2), 73-77, 2006.

/2/ CHROMČÍKOVÁ, M. – VOKELOVÁ, J. - MICHÁLKOVÁ, J. - LIŠKA, M. - MACHÁČEK, J. - GEDEON, O. - SOLTÉSZ, V.: *Chemical durability of gamma-irradiated glass fibrous insulation*. *J. Nuclear Technology* 193, 297-305, 2016.

/3/ SOLTÉSZ, V. - Et Al.: *Chemical durability of glass thermal insulation fibers in borate and phosphate water solutions*. *Advanced Materials Research* 363, 2008.